

Impact Study

Environmental & Biodiversity Preservation

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Context

According to the latest [Global Assessment Report on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services](#), 75% of global land surface is significantly altered, 66% of the ocean area is experiencing increasing cumulative impacts and over 85% of wetlands area has been lost. The report further suggests that around one million species already face extinction, many within decades, unless action is taken to reduce the intensity of drivers of biodiversity loss.

To address and mitigate these worrying statistics, scientists and conservationists are leveraging data from biodata resources to inform conservation efforts and preserve important ecosystems. By providing access to data, tools and training, biodata resources are informing fact-based decisions and policies that align with our most up-to-date understanding of the complex interplay between animal and plant species across the world, including how human activities are affecting them.

This series of case studies explores how biodata resources have underpinned efforts to preserve biodiversity and the environment.

Protecting vulnerable species

The [IUCN Red List of Threatened Species](#) is a database that holds data on more than 163,000 species of animal, fungi and plants, assessing species on their global conservation status and extinction risk. Today, more than 45,300 species (or 28% of those assessed in the database) are threatened by extinction.

Using data about the Mediterranean monk seal from this resource, the TUI Care Foundation and the Mediterranean Conservation Society launched the [‘Sea the Change’](#) programme in Turkey in 2024. As of the latest assessment in 2023, the Mediterranean monk seal is classed as [‘vulnerable’](#): with only 440-600 mature individuals left in the species face a high risk of extinction in the wild.

TUI’s ‘Sea the Change’ aims to enhance data collection in the Sarigerme region by monitoring coastal caves. It will also establish a dry platform to provide additional ground for seals to rest and for the pupping seasons. Finally, the programme will work with government agencies to establish protection zones around caves known to host seal activity or pupping. Importantly, these activities are closely aligned with the [conservation actions](#) that are listed in the IUCN Red List of Threatened Species.

The programme also focuses on awareness raising activities with locals, tourists and businesses in tourism hotspots in southwest Türkiye to encourage conservation-friendly behaviours. It is expected that this programme will train 700 people in marine conservation, including local professionals such as boat tour operators and hotel staff.

Collecting and sharing data to steward important ecosystems

Mozambique is one of the world's poorest countries and has a high dependency on natural resources. At the same time, the population is rising, which puts growing pressure on biodiversity. The Mozambican government has made a decision to address poverty through [sustainable development](#), and information is therefore needed on biodiversity priorities to inform land-use decision-making.

The Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) leads the European-Union-funded '[Biodiversity Information for Development](#)' (BID) programme, which aims to enhance capacity for effective mobilisation and use of biodiversity data in research and policy in the '[ACP](#)' nations across Africa, the Caribbean and the Pacific.

Through the BID programme, the Instituto de Investigação Agrária de Moçambique has joined with their international partners to produce a checklist and national Red List of endemic and near-endemic species for plants, birds, reptiles, amphibians, insects and fish. Their objective was to create a land-use decision-making tool, leveraging more than 5,000 specimen and observation records and accessible through the [Biodiversity Network of Mozambique \(BioNoMo\)](#) – a biodiversity data portal which serves as a [national repository](#) of fauna and flora native to Mozambique.

Similarly, the [Ocean Biodiversity Information System](#) is a gateway to global ocean biodiversity and biogeographic data, covering [50 million observations](#) of 120,000 marine species from 2,000 datasets provided by nearly 600 institutions in 56 countries. Growing at around a rate of 3 million records per year, OBIS holds a wealth of data to be used for ocean ecosystem preservation.

Stewarding ecosystems not only requires the data itself, but also infrastructures that may be unaffordable in some countries and specialist skills. OBIS [has been providing](#) a range of benefits across the world, including source data hosting free of charge to OBIS Nodes who do not have these capabilities in their host institutions and capacity building to its current and prospective users. Working with the [OceanTeacher Global Academy](#), OBIS has provided training courses in data management, data analysis and decision support in multiple languages. OBIS has seen a multiplication of training efforts in countries where they have previously organised courses, which represents a direct return on investment and helps increase the distribution and development of knowledge on marine data management and use worldwide.

Understanding the role of humans in ancient extinction events

[AlphaFold](#) is an AI system that formulates predictions of a protein's 3D structure based on its amino acid sequence. Its predictions are made publicly available via AlphaFold DB, which covers the 3D structure of over 200 million proteins catalogued in [UniProt](#).

AlphaFold's capabilities have been combined with a range of biodata resources to solve a [50,000 year old mystery](#) in Australia. It was known that local populations used to consume the eggs of an extinct bird, but morphological and geochemical methods were neither able to identify which one nor whether human activity had played a role in the extinction of said species. The candidate species included two extinct birds: the giant flightless Genyornis, and the extinct giant malleefowl, Progura. To answer this question, [scientists](#) extracted ancient protein sequences from burnt eggshells and estimated their evolutionary affinity with a range of extant taxa. Through interdisciplinary efforts and the use of sophisticated data and digital infrastructure, including the Bird 10,000 Genomes project AlphaFold, the team discovered that humans did, indeed, play a role in the extinction of Genyornis.

Importantly, the above study was underpinned by a broader range of biodata resources: preliminary searches conducted to inform the development of these findings included the use of the [NCBI database](#) as well as the [Common Repository of Adventitious Proteins](#). Furthermore, the proteomics datasets generated have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium via the [Proteomics Identifications Database \(PRIDE\)](#) hosted by EMBL.

Conclusions

The case studies presented in this series demonstrate ways in which the wealth of information available in biodata resources can help conservation organisations and governments in making informed decisions, prioritising their efforts and developing targeted strategies to protect vulnerable species and ecosystems. It is important to appreciate that community engagement, awareness raising, and skills development are equally relevant in this context, as targeted interventions require cooperation from local communities and an in-depth understanding of the local context that local scientists are uniquely placed to provide. It is, therefore, key to secure sustained funding for these complementary responsibilities that extend beyond the provision of data and infrastructures.

In addition, the importance of interconnectivity across biodata resources cannot be overstated. Some of the above examples have clearly benefited from a breadth of biodata resources at different stages of the research process, showing how these can unlock the answer to critical questions about Earth and its inhabitants and, ultimately, help us steward the planet for future generations.

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Appendix – Resources discussed

Resources	About
AlphaFold DB (AlphaFold Protein Structure Database)	<p>AlphaFold DB is a database providing open access (with a generous CC BY license) to the predicted 3D structure of over 200 million proteins, nearly all catalogued proteins known to science, based on their amino acid sequence. The predictions are computationally generated by an AI system, AlphaFold, developed by EMBL-EBI and Google DeepMind. The site also provides downloads for the human proteome, alongside another 47 organism proteomes key to research and global health.</p>
Bird 10,000 Genomes (B10K) Project	<p>The B10K project is an initiative which generates representative draft genome sequences of all living bird species, building on the Avian Phylogenomics Project.</p> <p>The B10K project has published the avian's family tree species tree, as well as releasing 363 genomes representing a total of 92% of all bird families.</p>
Common Repository of Adventitious Proteins	<p>The Common Repository of Adventitious Proteins is a catalog of proteins that frequently appear in experiments related to proteins, often as a result of accidental presence or unavoidable contamination.</p> <p>Proteins in this list include common laboratory proteins, proteins added by accident through dust or physical contact and proteins used as molecular weight or mass spectrometry quantitation standards.</p>
Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF)	<p>The GBIF is an international data infrastructure and network that provides open access to data about all types of life. Established in 2001 the resource contains hundreds of millions of species occurrence records alongside resources like datasets, DNA barcodes and details of thousands of peer-reviewed papers using its data.</p>

Resources	About
<p>International Union for Conservation of Nature's Red List of Threatened Species (IUCN Red List)</p>	<p>The IUCN Red List is the most comprehensive resource on the global extinction risk status of animal, plant and fungus species. This resource was established in 1964 and currently holds data on over 163,000 species, with more than 45,300 species (28%) currently threatened with extinction.</p> <p>The resource is often referred to as a Barometer of Life and holds a wealth of information beyond the species and extinction risk status, such as population size, habitat and threats. Availability of this information can support conservation decisions and minimise the decline in biodiversity.</p>
<p>National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI)</p>	<p>The NCBI is a comprehensive resource for biological and biomedical information. It features a number of databases related to genomics, proteins and associated literature. It serves as the central hub for researchers, clinicians and students to access biomedical information, with tools and educational resources to support this.</p>
<p>Ocean Biodiversity Information System (OBIS)</p>	<p>The Ocean Biodiversity Information System provides open access to data and information on marine biodiversity, aimed for use in science, conservation and sustainable development. It contains over 130 million presence records, more than 190,000 species and 5,000 datasets.</p>
<p>The Biodiversity Network of Mozambique (BioNoMo)</p>	<p>BioNoMo is a national repository of biodiversity data which aggregates records of plants and animals in Mozambique from observations of flora and fauna, and from specimens from biological collections. As of 2023, it hosted a total of 273,172 records.</p> <p>This tool is used by Mozambican institutions to achieve sustainable development in the country.</p>
<p>UniProt</p>	<p>UniProt is the world's leading high-quality, comprehensive, and freely accessible resource of protein sequences and functional annotation, featuring the expert-curated core UniProtKB/Swiss-Prot. UniProt is mainly supported by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI), EMBL, and the US National Institutes of Health (NIH).</p>

Global Biodata Coalition

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